

Integrated pest management—other pests

Aphelenchoides besseyi in irrigated upland and lowland rice during dry and wet seasons

C. C. Huelma, J. C. Prot, S. D. Merca, and T. W. Mew, IRRI

Aphelenchoides besseyi, the causal agent of white-tip disease, is the only seedborne rice parasitic nematode. According to quarantine regulations, seed lots used for international germplasm exchange must be free of *A. besseyi*; those found positive during phytosanitary certification are destroyed. It is essential to produce seeds free of *A. besseyi* to prevent loss of valuable seed materials. *A. besseyi* infestation can be avoided by using nematode-free seeds and planting in nematode-free fields.

To determine the field conditions under which *A. besseyi* development is limited, we conducted a survey on the irrigated lowland and upland IRRI experimental farms during four consecutive rice-growing seasons. The IRRI fields have the Maahas (Guadalupe) series of soil profile. Irrigated lowland fields have clay to silty clay soil texture with pH of 5.7-7.2. Upland fields have silty clay to silty loam soil texture with pH 5.5-7.1. The temperature from 1979 to 1992 averaged 27 °C (15.2-38.2 °C). April is the hottest month and December,

Samples analyzed, average number of *Aphelenchoides besseyi* per 13-g seed sample, and frequency of occurrence (F = % of infested samples) of the nematode in 1989 and 1990 DS and WS rice crops on the IRRI irrigated (IR) and upland (UR) rice farms.

	Samples (no.)	Average number/sample	Frequency
IR 1989 DS	204	0.9	9.3
UR 1989 DS	26	0	0
IR 1989 WS	973	1.8	21.2
UR 1989 WS	219	2.7	18.7
IR 1990 DS	733	0.7	14.9
UR 1990 DS	286	0.5	0.7
IR 1990 WS	747	1.1	7.1
UR 1990 WS	297	0.7	8.1

the coldest. Annual rainfall (1979-92) averaged 2090.7 mm and the average humidity, 88%. Wet season (WS), from June to November, and dry season (DS), from December to May, are the major seasons. On the upland farm, upland rice is rainfed during WS and irrigated using sprinklers during DS.

We collected seed samples at maturity of the 1989 and 1990 DS and WS crops to estimate frequency and abundance of *A. besseyi*. Two hundred thirty samples (one/field) were collected during 1989 DS, 1,192 samples during 1989 WS, 1,019 during 1990 DS, and 1,044 during the 1990 WS. Each sample was made of 25 panicles collected at random. Panicles were threshed. Thirteen grams of seed for each sample were incubated for 5 d at 28 °C in a Baermann funnel for nematode extraction. Average number of *A. besseyi* per sample and frequency of occurrence as a percentage of infested samples were calculated.

A. besseyi was detected on both irrigated lowland and upland rice in both

seasons (see table). Frequency of *A. besseyi* occurrence during WS on the upland and irrigated lowland farms was similar. Except for the upland rice farm where the nematode was not detected during 1989 DS, the average number of *A. besseyi* per sample under either condition and under either season was not significantly different when compared using ANOVA. *A. besseyi*, however, appears to be less frequent on the upland rice farm during the DS crop than on the irrigated farm during DS and WS crops and on the upland farm during WS.

The nematode needs high canopy humidity to infest the aerial part of the plant, a condition present in irrigated lowland with standing water. Multiplying seeds for international exchange under upland conditions during DS may reduce the risk of *A. besseyi* contamination. Using gravity flow irrigation instead of sprinkler irrigation may further reduce the occurrence of *A. besseyi* under upland conditions during DS. ■

The combination of nematodes, *Sesbania rostrata*, and rice: the two sides of the coin

J. C. Prot, IRRI

Sesbania rostrata has tremendous potential as a green manure crop for improving soil fertility in permanently or intermittently flooded rice ecosystems. An additional benefit of growing *S. rostrata* in lowland rice is the control of rice root nematodes, *Hirschmanniella* spp. Since 1983, five papers have been published reporting that *S. rostrata* could be used in rotation with rice to reduce field populations of *Hirschmanniella mucronata* and *H. oryzae*, which damage irrigated rice. The coin, however, has two sides.

Rice root nematodes are not the only nematode pests of rice. More than 200 species of plant-parasitic nematodes have been reported to be associated with rice. Among these, the root-knot nematodes, *Meloidogyne* spp., are major pests of rainfed rice, causing swelling and galls throughout the root system. Although

Number of second-stage *M. graminicola* juveniles obtained from 3 g of roots of rice cultivar UPLRi-5 and *S. rostrata* grown under upland and irrigated conditions 60 d after plants were infested with 5,000 nematodes.

Crop	Condition under which plants were grown	
	Upland	Irrigated
Rice (UPLRi-5)	20,424	3,104
<i>S. rostrata</i>	20,165	3

Galls of *M. graminicola* on roots of *S. rostrata*.

they do not cause specific symptoms on the aboveground parts of the plant, they can cause severe growth reduction, chlorosis, wilting of plants, and 20-70% yield reduction in infested fields.

M. graminicola, the rice root-knot nematode, is widely distributed in rainfed upland and lowland ricefields in South and Southeast Asia, especially in light-textured soils. It is considered to be an important pest in rainfed lowland areas in India and northeast Thailand.

S. rostrata, unfortunately, is a very good host for *M. graminicola* when grown in nonflooded soils (see figure and table). Cropping it before rice in nonflooded soils infested by rice root-knot nematodes may increase their number tremendously. This increase in *M. graminicola* may cause increased yield losses, eliminating the benefit expected from cultivating the green manure crop. This is the other side of the coin.

S. rostrata has tremendous potential as a green manure crop. Under rainfed conditions, however, it must be used with caution. It is hazardous to grow *S. rostrata* in rainfed ricefields where *M. graminicola* is present. Leguminous crops resistant to *M. graminicola* should be identified as alternatives to *S. rostrata* in rainfed lowland rice areas infested with the nematode. ■

Environment

Climate change and rice

In March 1994, IRRI convened an international symposium that reviewed the broad issues of global climate and its effect on rice growth and production. The posters displayed at the symposium appear in a slightly modified form in this section. We hope you find these notes to be a valuable source of information.

Regional distribution of harvested rice area (million ha) in major rice-growing, less developed countries in 1985. IRRI, 1989.

Region	Irrigated rice	Rainfed rice	Deepwater rice	Upland rice	Total
South Asia	19.2	24.3	8.8	7.9	60.2
East Asia	32.2	1.9	-	0.7	34.8
Southeast Asia	12.0	12.6	3.6	3.3	31.5
Latin America	2.2	0.4	-	4.5	7.1
Africa	1.0	1.3	0.2	2.1	4.6
Total	66.6	40.5	12.6	18.5	138.2

Methane emission from ricefields

H U Neue, R. Wassmann, R. S. Lantin, M. C. Alberto, and J. B. Aduna, IRRI

The increase in atmospheric CH_4 concentration has been recognized during the past decade. The current amount of methane in the atmosphere is 4700 Tg. The total annual global emission of CH_4 is estimated to be 500 Tg, about 70% of which is biogenic in origin. Flooded ricefields are probably one of the largest agricultural sources of atmospheric CH_4 .

Flooding a ricefield cuts off the oxygen supplied by the atmosphere to the soil; this results in the fermentation of soil organic matter. CH_4 is a major end product of this process. Flooded ricefields release CH_4 to the atmosphere by diffusion, ebullition, or through the

Scheme of methane production, oxidation, and emission in a flooded ricefield.

rice plants, which mediate the transport of CH_4 from the reduced soil to the atmosphere (see figure). Much of the CH_4 formed in the anaerobic soil may remain entrapped in the soil and is oxidized to CO_2 .

Rice is the only major grain crop that is grown almost exclusively for human food. One hundred forty million ha of rice are harvested annually. In developed countries, ricefields are irrigated because it increases production potential. In less

developed countries, only 50% of the harvested rice area is irrigated but it accounts for more than 70% of yield. Rainfed ricefields, which are prone to droughts and floods, make up 30% of the rice area, and upland rice, 13% (see table). It is estimated that irrigated and rainfed ricefields emit annually up to 100 Tg CH_4 . ■